

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Biosecurity in times of COVID19 or how to take it seriously

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Abstract

The biosafety associated with biomedical laboratories and the biosafety associated with clinical establishments do not seem to go together. There is a biosafety manual in each country and there are basic biosafety standards that do not seem to be applied or taught in specialized centers.

Thus, along with thanking the great participation of the medical establishment and associated professions, we must not lower our guard against this pathogen or any other that surrounds us. Although the biosafety standards are taught in some of the higher education centers, they are not necessarily followed by the same ones who mention them in their speech, as if they only applied to others.

This article may cause resentment, however, it is a national reality that I hope will not be repeated in many countries. Nor do I intend to draw attention to the misuse of clothing or instruments, but rather to diminish this fashion and that we recognize our fragility in the face of the world around us.

Keywords: Biosecurity, SARS-CoV-2, COVID19, Training, infected, deaths, transmission

Introduction

In times of COVID19, biosecurity has not been considered either, just go to any national health center to see distinguished medical professionals wearing an open apron and with the typical stethoscope hanging around their neck in places far from their patient care, such as streets and cafeterias, for instance.

For some years we have witnessed the aforementioned, which incidentally, is required of students, but not strictly practiced by teachers of Higher Education Houses. To this extent, perhaps some higher education centers consider the issue of biosafety, but without the necessary strict measure that it entails. Obviously, a biomedical laboratory must observe, maintain and demand to comply with basic biosafety standards, such as the proper use of an apron, hair taken, not eating, not drinking and others that would undoubtedly contribute to the proper use of facilities, for example (1)

A medical establishment, where the permanence and flow of pathogens could be greater than that of another non-medical facility, should consider the use of exclusive clothing in the place of patient care. However, in times of COVID19 we have witnessed interviews with renowned doctors or their participation in morning sessions with an apron on, including their stethoscope. The above, of not using clothing other than that used with their patients, is clearly one of the maneuvers that could go against those mentioned as the use of a mask and hand washing for at least 20 seconds.

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There is another similar custom that today could be cause for concern. There are students or professionals who wear their clothing outside the medical establishment, as part of their wardrobe when traveling between home and work. A typical case is their movement on the Santiago Metropolitan Train (Figures 1, 2 and 3)

Figure 1 on the train

Figure 2 Leaving the station

Figure 3 On the street

This "fashion" may be due to the urgency of changing clothes when starting and finishing a job in a biomedical area. Is it justified then? Apparently not, because using the same clothing inside and outside the medical establishment could facilitate the movement of pathogens of human and veterinary interest. But who cares?

According to authorities, in our country, around 15 million people have been vaccinated against SARS-CoV-2 and around 39 thousand have died. Such numbers are not without concern, especially if we could put a stop to the number of deaths [2].

Biosafety measures must be emphasized, especially for biomedical personnel who have been overloaded with work since the start of this pandemic.

However, in the absence of a COVID19-type situation, the issue has not been taken with the seriousness that it entails, there is no awareness of the danger posed by existing environmental pathogens ... Is it perhaps a product of their small size?

Conclusion

It is necessary to complement both the clinical and biosafety standards applied to personnel who are in contact with COVID19 positive patients, which could reduce the number of deaths involved.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

This article was born from the vision of professionals or students who work or do their practice in a health center in Santiago de Chile and use the Metropolitan train to get around

Statement of informed consent

The figures that appear in this article were taken by the author of the article and would not need consent, since the mask or the physical position protects the innocent

References

- [1] Laboratory Biosafety Manual, 4th edition. WHO. 2020. Available in: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240011311>
- [2] Plan Nacional de Vacunacion COVID19. 2021. Available in: <https://www.gob.cl/yomevacuno/#vacunados>